

D3.1: State-of-art in XR policy debates

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ABSTRACT:	This report aims to map out the current regulatory and governance environments surrounding government, industry, and civil society stakeholders in relation to XR technologies. To identify existing EU governance and regulatory gaps regarding XR, this report is guided by the current state-of-art in regulatory, policy, and governance discourse in various areas of application and concern. Informed by discussions on the aforementioned elements, this report proposes a regulatory risk assessment approach for XR technology, identifying associated physical, mental, social, legal and abuse of power risks.
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Executive Summary

The project XR4HUMAN focuses on an ethical and human-centred development process for XR technologies. This report, developed as part of the XR4Human project, maps out the regulatory and governance environments surrounding government, industry, and civil society stakeholders in relation to XR technologies, taking the current state-of-art in European regulation, policy and governance discourse as guidance to identify gaps within EU regulation and governance in terms of XR technology benefits, risks, and impacts. For the purposes of this report, Extended Reality (XR) is considered to be an umbrella term that encompasses the following technologies: Augmented Reality (AR), which overlays the user's physical environment with virtual content; Virtual Reality (VR), which creates fully artificial environments (e.g. the so-called 'metaverse'); and Mixed Reality (MR), which blends physical and digital elements into real-time interactive spaces.

Beyond the concept of XR, there are a variety of functionalities, including input, processing, distribution, and recording. Such components illustrate the complexity of XR, but also the potential for technological integration, resulting in better development and accessibility. The integration of XR with other technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) will further enhance the capabilities of XR. However, interoperability issues will also shape the future technical development of XR. It is recommended that internationally coordinated standardization of hardware and software, with a user-centred and socially responsible perspective, is pursued, as this can support stable and purposeful development of the technology. This is important because XR is currently being used in a wide range of sectors and industries, and these applications will only increase in the coming years as the accessibility of XR hardware improves.

The media and entertainment sector is the leading XR industry, with applications including gaming, social media, live entertainment, and adult entertainment. XR applications have proven to be beneficial in times of uncertainty in the entertainment sector, for instance allowing live in-person events to take place in virtual environments when various restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic made in-person events unviable. However, XR in media and entertainment presents various challenges and limitations. Physical risks from XR technology may arise from rapid movement commands given by XR hardware/software to play games, which could seriously injure users or others around them. The psychological risks of XR technology for media consumers arise from two main sources: the level of immersion, which can lead to addiction and depersonalisation, and interactions with other users, which can be abusive. XR applications in media and entertainment pose more privacy and surveillance risks than traditional social media/internet usage due to the collection of biometric data and lack of regulation regarding such information collection/management. While innovations have been developed to address some of the privacy and surveillance risks, the XR industry has sometimes resisted such developments.

XR has been used in the work and production sector to improve various elements of the manufacturing process and employee training. Despite the obvious benefits in terms of cost efficiency, XR applications in the workplace can have a negative impact on employees. Differences in digital literacy levels need to be addressed to mitigate the skills gap that may develop because of increased XR use in the workplace. This will be possible through an EU-wide XR ecosystem that promotes relevant skills through education, training, and professional development. Another risk is that XR devices give employers greater access to their employees' personal data, including biometrics, which can be used for intrusive monitoring in the workplace and opaque performance evaluation. Recommendations include providing training to ensure that personal data taken at the source is anonymous or cannot lead to a future identification of employees. Finally, there are risks posed by cybersecurity breaches of the XR operating system or applications running on the device, which could expose both employees and companies to the unwanted disclosure of sensitive information.

The medical and healthcare field has been using XR tools for some time, to assist in the training of professionals, and patient diagnosis and treatment of both physical and mental illnesses. In addition, XR devices are becoming an essential tool for psychological research. The benefits of using XR in this field are primarily focused on cost savings, and the adaptability to the needs of patients, therapists, and medical staff. Challenges and limitations identified in the application of XR technology in healthcare include hygiene of devices, inadequate legislation regarding the processing of patient's biometric data collected from XR devices, and various psychosocial and medical consequences XR usage has on individual health in general – including simulator sickness, social isolation, PTSD from unexpected horror/violence exposure, and lack of ground truth. The development of mandatory data protection guidelines for managing patient data collected from XR applications in healthcare settings is essential to fostering further usage and advancement of XR in this sector.

In the marketing and retail sector, the current state of the art in XR applications allows consumers to engage with offered goods in their own houses through AR, with the future potential for retailers to offer fully virtual shops accessed via VR devices. The tourism industry also utilizes XR for advertising by showing the most vivid representations of travel destinations possible, which has been found to increase the intention of potential tourists to travel to the advertised location. Privacy concerns are the key issue highlighted in academic and stakeholder reports, given the biometric data these devices may collect from consumers. These data can also lead to violations of consumer rights, with XR technology having the potential to be used by advertisers for manipulation purposes. Intellectual property rights can be easily infringed in XR environments, which can be exacerbated by problems in enforcing these rights in such contexts.

XR is currently used by the military, police and emergency services. Its benefits to the security industry include the ability to simulate high-risk scenarios for training purposes without directly exposing personnel to these risks. For instance, military VR applications can be used to train prospective soldiers in various aspects of combat situations and situational awareness prior to their deployment, as well as to deal with the effects of deployment in actual soldiers, such as PTSD. However, the use of XR in the security sector exposes operations to significant risks of leakage of sensitive data and classified information, which can even threaten safety of personnel and national security. Design decisions also need to be reconsidered in relation to this field, as life-threatening situations could occur when security personnel use XR devices that impair environmental awareness.

XR is widely used within education, in various fields such as medicine, STEM, and the humanities, and to meet specific student needs. XR allows students to immerse themselves in environments which they would not otherwise be able to experience and simulate practical tasks or operations that may be too risky or expensive to perform in real-life. For students with disabilities, XR gives them the opportunity to improve their physical education, and communication and collaboration skills, thus providing better opportunities for integration with their peers. However, XR can also have a negative impact on these students, as the technology may not be suitable for some disabilities and therefore not inclusive for all. Other challenges and limitations surrounding XR applications in education are largely data related, given the large amounts of personal data that can be collected from students using XR devices. On the other hand, stakeholders have argued that EU's strict data protection regulation may hinder educational XR usage in some members of the Union. In addition, low levels of technological literacy among educators and funding inequalities across the EU, could further hamper the adoption of such technologies.

For urban planning and conservation, XR is applied to produce 3D models of above-ground infrastructure of cities, known as 'digital twins', which include buildings, transportation networks, parks, and other infrastructural features using 2D/3D imagery. XR used for urban planning and conservation purposes may expose the public to privacy and security threats, not only for users, but also for bystanders

who may be recorded when XR devices are used in public spaces. It is recommended that bystanders are made aware of the possibility of being recorded in a particular space where XR is in operation, and platforms should resist enabling persistent pseudo-anonymous identification or tracking of bystanders.

The overall potential of XR is therefore high in terms of technological innovation and growth and is considered important not only for the development of the above-mentioned markets, but also for the creation of new ones. The XR industry is expected to grow rapidly in the coming years thanks to the development of new VR/AR hardware that enables software/application development with far-reaching implications. However, compared to the US and Asian markets, the EU's position in the global XR market is challenged by awareness and demand for applications and investment, which hinders the scale-up of European companies. Fragmentation of hardware, software, content creation, regulations and entrepreneurial traditions in the EU XR realm require attention to meet the high for economic and employment growth expectations in the sector.

The potential growth of XR also depends on addressing the social implications of its use. XR users, particularly children, are exposed to a range of harms from harassment and grooming to gambling. Current age rating policies implemented by companies are cited as insufficient to reduce these harms, as the level of immersion in XR experiences is far greater than in traditional media and games. Such immersion can have other negative psychological effects on users, leading to depersonalisation and emotional investment in virtual worlds, which may result in users becoming less social in the real world and neglecting their real-life relationships. Tactics used to manipulate political beliefs, previously exposed in notorious cases such as Cambridge Analytica, may become stronger, with the creation of deepfakes, high levels of immersion and additional data collected from XR devices making political manipulation more precise and fake news more convincing. An urgent and effective response is therefore essential for the functioning of European democracy.

This report concludes with a proposed regulatory risk assessment approach for XR technology, identifying physical and mental risks, social risks, abuse of power, and legal risks, and incorporating perspectives from diversity, inclusivity, accessibility, and interoperability. This assessment shall be contrasted with the current EU regulatory framework applicable to XR, including the AI Act, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the copyright regime, the Digital Services Act (DSA), and the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), among others. This comparison will result in a regulatory gap report to be further developed by the XR4Human project.

1 Introduction

The project XR4HUMAN focuses on an ethical and human-centered development process for XR technologies. It involves representation of industry, consumers, regulators and academia to generate European standards for XR. As described in its basic concept, the project supports end-user decision-making and, through focus on inclusivity, ensure that every European company and citizen has the potential to take advantage of what XR can offer, paving the way towards a strong and competitive ecosystem whilst building public trust and acceptance.

The specific objectives of XR4Human are to:

1. Engage European XR companies and other stakeholders towards the uptake of the XR Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users.
2. Engage European XR stakeholders through a permanent digital European forum towards the co-creation and uptake of XR4Human guidance and tools.
3. Map, examine, evaluate, and provide a conceptual and normative framework on the ethical issues (including issues of inclusivity) arising in XR technologies.
4. Map, examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on related regulatory and governance issues arising in XR technologies.
5. Co-create an Interoperability Guidance Document.
6. Co-create a European Code of Conduct for Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centred XR Technologies for developers and producers.
7. Record and demonstrate the practical application of the XR Code of Conduct through good practices, failure cases, test cases, and use cases.
8. Provide an online repository of test cases to allow developers to demonstrate evidence of adherence to best practices.
9. Support informed decision making of the end user XR community for the acquisition and use of XR technology by an XR rating system and a supportive toolbox of informational and educational materials.

The current document deals with the 4th objective of “Mapping of the Regulatory and Governance Issues of XR”. The overall objective of the relevant work package (WP3) is to map, examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on the related regulatory and governance issues arising in XR technologies. This has been further broken down to more specific objectives:

- Map the regulatory and governance landscape in terms of government, industry, and civil society stakeholders.
- Analyse the current state-of-art in European policy and governance discussions on XR technologies.
- Analyse the current state-of-art in the regulatory landscape relevant to XR technologies.
- Identify governance and regulatory gaps in terms of benefits, risks and impacts associated with XR technologies.

As a first step towards a detailed regulatory gap analysis and the creation of policy recommendations, this report aims at providing an overview of the policy issues in XR as they are discussed currently in Europe. As with any area in Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) developments, policy debates rarely focus on the specificities of technological advances. The focus of every STI policy is to ensure a beneficial impact on human society, the economy, and the environment, while providing

safeguards against unintended consequences. The discussions around these issues are therefore a mix between scientific facts and perspectives on societal norms and ethics. Ultimately, policy outcomes are a compromise between facts and values.

XR technologies represent a new development in STI that uses well known ICT applications in entertainment, media, education, training, etc. but with an important twist. XR technologies “extend” the personal experience to a point of perhaps achieving a complete overlap between real and artificial. The result can be a mixed reality that is neither real nor non-real. And this is the main point of contention and debate in this type of technologies. Whether creating a fully artificial environment where the “real” self is located, or whether they enhance reality to a desirable level that does not really “exist”, XR technologies are the par excellence intimate technologies. They can penetrate the individual and society in ways that never existed before and as such, they are posing new challenges to our norms and values that must be expressed in policy making.

XR technologies are to be found in every major aspect of social life. From work to entertainment, education, trade, health, and security, XR applications are making an impact (see Figure 1.1). Their penetration in everyday life for the majority of the population (at least in developed countries) is such, that it has become imperative to discuss possible implications of their applications.

Fig. 1.1. XR fields of applications (Kind et al, 2019: 2f.)

When considering the implications of XR technologies, a host of key questions arise such as:

How do XR technologies change the status quo in the private sphere and in the working environment? What are the possible physical and mental effects accompanying significant use of these technologies? What are the effects of XR technologies in the economy? How do they impact on the drive for economic digitalisation? How do XR technologies affect societal services such as health care and education? What are the pros and cons of the existing applications and what are the main future challenges? Is the current regulatory environment appropriate for the development of XR technologies?

Are the identifiable risks, challenges and opportunities covered? What are the regulatory gaps and how can they be dealt with?

These are examples of questions that will lead the policy analysis part of the project. Following, is a review of the state-of-art in policy debates around XR technologies. It is the result of desktop research analysing the existing literature in the field and seeking to be fully inclusive in terms of societal and disciplinary perspectives. The approach taken starts with a perspective on the relevant definitions, the current technical state and perceived economic potential. We will then provide an assessment of the debates in major XR application fields: media and entertainment, work and production processes, medical processes and health care, marketing and trade, and education. A short review of the economic implications will follow, along with our view on the social risks and the necessary risk assessment analysis that should feed the subsequent regulatory gap analysis in the project. The aim of this and the subsequent analysis is nothing less than to aid and improve the governance of XR and advice the policy making process.

2 Definitions

To date, little consensus exists on the substantive meaning and conceptual scope of XR technologies targeted by this study. Given that both academic and industry documents use Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR), Augmented Virtuality (AV), Virtual Reality (VR), and Extended Reality (XR) terminology in diverse ways, this section aims to provide a common reference framework for our further analysis (Flavián et al., 2019; Rauschnabel et al., 2022).

Augmented Reality (AR) technology creates enhanced, hybrid experiences of the physical environment in real-time. AR refines a user's perceptible reality through computing devices. More specifically, it superimposes virtual content in the form of text, images, or virtual objects on the user's field of vision (ITAS, 2019). In other words, AR produces a computer-generated extension of a user's physical environment – or “local presence” (Rauschnabel et al., 2022). Depending on the level of local presence, AR technology supports various levels of virtual projection that can range from assisted reality (low) to mixed reality (high) (Rauschnabel et al., 2022). In line with Ecorys (2021), we define AR technology as a means of overlaying digital information onto the user's natural field of vision for purposes of enhancement rather than complete substitution.

Virtual Reality (VR) technology creates artificial, viewer-centred experiences that are separate from the physical, real-time environment (ITAS, 2019; Snijders et al., 2020). Suitable hardware (e.g., headsets, haptic gloves, virtual rooms, treadmills) is required to enable users to access VR spaces and interact with virtual objects or each other through avatars (Ecorys, 2021). Most importantly, VR technology affords various levels of what Rauschnabel et al. (2022) term “telepresence”, i.e., a subjective ‘sense of presence’ in virtual space. As the Rathenau Instituut (2020) explains, such immersive technology operates by compiling “kinematic fingerprints” from tracking user's motion via biometric data points such as head, body, and eye movements, facial expressions, and gestures. Depending on the sophistication of VR spaces, VR appliances can produce a spectrum of immersive experiences that range from atomistic (low) to holistic (high) digital sensory impression (Rauschnabel et al., 2022). In line with the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) (2020), we define VR as a means of generating fully immersive virtual experiences within virtual environments. Recognizing the intimate and data rich character of VR, we furthermore identify VR as a technology that requires first and foremost responsible research, development, and use.

Augmented Virtuality (AV) technology creates enhanced, hybrid experiences of virtual spaces in real time. AV refines computer-generated virtual spaces by superimposing real-world content on the user's field of vision through computing devices. In other words, AV offers a strongly mediated immersive

experience that is dominated by virtual objects but not completely sealed-off from the user's physical environment. Considering that AV is more commonly defined by academia as a sub-set of VR technology, MR technology, or one that overlaps with both (Flavián et al., 2019; Milgram & Kishino, 1994; Wedel et al., 2020), and is not often used in policy reports, AV is excluded as an independent concept term in this study.

Mixed Reality (MR) technology creates hybrid, artificial experiences that seamlessly integrate physical environments, and computer-generated landscapes. MR involves various elements of AR and VR, which afford the user to interact with both physical and artificial stimuli/objects in mediated real-time spaces (Ecorys, 2021). Due to its "mixed" nature, MR is used to describe a wide range of VR, AR, or "realistic" AR appliances (Rauschnabel et al., 2022). Milgram and Kishino (1994) popularized the idea of MR being any environment that exists anywhere alongside the "virtuality continuum", meaning between the two extremes of completely real and completely virtual spaces (cf. Mhaidli & Schaub, 2021). In line with the general academic and policy consensus, we identify MR as a technology that operates as a middle step of the reality-virtuality continuum (Milgram & Kishino, 1994).

Extended Reality (XR) technology encompasses all technologies that overlay a user's physical environment with virtual content (AR), produce complete artificial environments (VR), and merge physical and digital elements into interactive real-time spaces (MR) (Mhaidli & Schaub, 2021). In current policy discussions on innovative technology research and development, XR has emerged as a critical umbrella term to index a wide range of existing and future immersive technologies (Ecorys, 2021). Given that VR, AR, and MR cannot be clearly distinguished from each other in principle (ITAS, 2019; Rauschnabel et al., 2022), we use the concept of XR to describe any technological appliances that open up new ways in human-computer interaction. Other than MR, this study defines XR to include technologies from within the virtuality continuum, as well as the extreme of completely virtual spaces (Rauschnabel et al., 2022) (see Fig. 2.1 below).

Fig. 2.1. XR as an umbrella term for AR and VR (Rauschnabel et al., 2022).

3 Technical State and Economic Potential

XR technologies consist of a combination of a number of software and hardware applications. There is no standard constellation that creates a VR, AR or any other type of an XR technology. At the same time, the pace of development is such that new combinations are possible and new applications of existing technologies are entering the XR world. Overall, one can categorise the various aspects of XR technologies under the following headings (Kind et al., 2019):

- Input: Camera systems, sensors, lasers, infrared, data gloves, treadmills, controllers, capture software, 360° video software, tracking algorithms.
- Processing: Image scene generator/graphics processor, image editing software, video game engines, content creation software.
- Distribution: Distribution platforms, distribution software
- Recording: wired or wireless HMDs (Head-Mounted Display), CAVE systems (Cave Automatic Virtual Environment), spectacle lenses, contact lenses, headphones, gloves, etc.

This shows the complexity of an XR but also its potential for technology integration that few other developments can achieve. In terms of accessibility, one can argue that most of these components have already reached or will be soon reaching, mass production capabilities. For instance, XR headsets (e.g., Oculus Quest, HoloLens 2, Varjo XR1, NReal, etc.) have reached an advanced stage of development and are readily available and affordable for a large segment of the consumer population. In short, usability, quality and price of headsets have achieved a satisfactory ratio to guarantee mass market penetration. The same can be said for the generation of imagery whereby 360-degree cameras and 3D video generation with good volumetric capture, is the norm. Nowadays 3D rendering engines are compatible with those used by the movie industry, rapidly evolving to producing highly realistic imagery. This, combined with advances in tactile and olfactory input, can develop into a fully artificial life experience.

Further capabilities of XR technologies will be unleashed with developments in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies, that in turn are depending on speed and quality of data input. 5G technology will expand the available bandwidth and provide the necessary speed to allow cloud-computing for XR applications that will translate into unrestricted accessibility and full development capacity. There are currently test beds in various European cities via for instance The Open Spatial Computing Platform from Open AR Cloud. Further capabilities (e.g., olfactory applications) are foreseen with the advent of 6G technology that is already being tested in closed laboratory settings (European Commission et al., 2022) (European Commission et al., 2022).

Amongst the technical aspects that will influence the development of XR technologies, the issue of interoperability is of particular significance. As the diversity of hardware and software facets increases in a rapid manner, standardization issues gain in importance. International standards are required for a smooth and meaningful development in the field, and these should be based on a user-centric and socially responsible perspective (see for instance the section on urban planning). Standards such as the WebXR, Open Geospatial Consortium's OGC, or the GeoPose, are examples interoperability possibilities in XR and Spatial Computing (Hsu et al., 2013).

Finally, it is worth mentioning that, within the XR field, VR and AR can have different market development and the same is true for their hardware and software components. At the same time, business-to-business (B2B) applications have also a distinct development that business-to-consumer (B2C) ones. As such, it is not easy to estimate the economic potential of the whole sector without breaking

it down to its constituent parts. Nevertheless, for the purposes of the current report, it suffices to accept the overall significant economic potential of the sector that requires unambiguous policies and a clear regulatory landscape.

4 Applications in Media and Entertainment

4.1 Overview and State-of-Art

In the EU, gaming makes up the largest market share of VR/AR, accounting for 29%. The rest of media and entertainment applications make up 19% of the EU VR/AR market (European Commission et al., 2022). Within the XR gaming industry, there are two formats which account for the majority of usage: metaverse experiences, and VR adaptations of traditional video games. A metaverse is an 'immersive and constant virtual 3D world where people interact by means of an avatar to carry out a wide range of activities' (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022, p.1). Examples of the most widely used metaverses across the globe include Horizon Worlds, Roblox, and VRChat.

In recent years, XR technology has been also utilised in the live entertainment, movie, and cultural industries. When the Covid-19 pandemic broke out and in-person live entertainment events were cancelled, VR technology allowed live shows to still take place but in the virtual realm and not the physical. Lost Horizon is an example of a live music event which was created during the Covid 19 pandemic, holding a two-day festival which was attended by 4.36 million people via VR (Lost Horizon, 2023). In recent years, many similar events, for instance through the children's metaverse platform 'Roblox', from world-renowned artists take place for fans to enjoy from their own homes via their VR hardware (Doyle, 2023).

Simultaneously, the adult entertainment industry accompanies the gaming industry in being leaders of VR content development (Snijders et al., 2020). While large VR hardware/software companies (Meta, Samsung, Sony) refuse to allow pornographic content onto their platforms, the market for such material within VR still exists and is developing. For example, VR pornography content is one of the fastest growing categories on the 'Pornhub' adult content website (Karpinski, 2021). Simon and Greitemeyer (2019) found in their study that individuals felt more physical excitement and had a more subjective and immersive experience when viewing a pornography video with a VR headset compared to watching it on a 2D screen. The application of XR in the adult entertainment industry includes the use of haptic sensations through other devices connected to the headset to deliver further sensory immersion into the adult content being consumed. A Dutch company 'Kiiroo' is an example of a European company currently offering such experiences to users through their combination of adult videos and teledildonic devices for stimulation (Karpinski, 2021).

4.2 Challenges and Limitations

In the EU, gaming makes up the largest market share of VR/AR, accounting for 29%. The rest of media and entertainment applications make up 19% of the EU VR/AR market (European Commission et al., 2022). Within the XR gaming industry, there are two formats which account for the majority of usage: metaverse experiences, and VR adaptations of traditional video games. A metaverse is an 'immersive and constant virtual 3D world where people interact by means of an avatar to carry out a wide range of activities' (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022, p.1). Examples of the most widely used metaverses across the globe include Horizon Worlds, Roblox, and VRChat.

4.2.1 Mental and Physical Risks

It has been observed in studies that video games played through VR technology provide a notably distinct experience when compared to being played on television. Wilson and McGill (2018) observed that VR had 'demonstrable effects' on players, as the immersive nature of VR technology results in the user 'subjectively and physiologically responds similarly to how they would' if the situation experienced in the VR game occurred in real life. If a user happens to be tricked into downloading malware or other viruses onto their VR device, a hacker may gain access to their device and manipulate their behaviour. Depending on the hacker's motive, social engineering will result in the user unintentionally carrying out acts which benefit the hacker.

In terms of physical risks, users may become ignorant of the real-life environment around them and may seriously harm themselves/others due to their senses being impaired and immersed in a virtual world. Physical risks presented to users from XR applications in media and entertainment need not be solely due to impact of one's physical environment, but also the commands given by the application in use. A study in Germany found a 31-year-old male patient had fractured his seventh cervical vertebra (lower neck) from playing a game on his VR headset, whereby rapid shoulder, arm, and head movements had to be made to the rhythm of visual and audio cues (Baur et al., 2021). These commands may require rapid movements, which Baur et al. (2021) conclude can result in injuries of the cervical spine.

The psychological risks posed by XR applications in media and entertainment are provoked from two sources: level of immersion and interactions with other users. The immersion into virtual reality through XR technologies can have adverse effects such as addiction and depersonalisation. Gedam et al. (2017) state that addiction related to the internet should be classified as its own mental disorder. With the added immersion that VR gives users, Snijder et al. (2020) remark that VR may be highly addictive, resulting in more extreme addiction and depersonalisation than is currently experienced with traditional social media and gaming mediums. Studies have already reported that some users have spent between 24 and 168 successive hours in virtual worlds (Snijders et al., 2020), with some experts believing that those who spend such amounts of time in virtual worlds will experience symptoms of depersonalisation such as feelings of detachment from bodily, identity or personal psychological processes (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). As the applications of XR in other fields, such as education and work and production, would not require a user to use hardware for longer than a working day, the private entertainment application carries these particular risks due to how long an individual spend in virtual realms in their own time.

Psychological risks can also come from social interactions with other VR users in metaverse environments. Using their avatars, users can harass one another verbally, but also mimic physical acts of harassment which are not possible to experience on traditional social media/gaming platforms. Researchers from SumOfUs conducted a study within Meta's virtual worlds (Horizon Worlds, Population One, Echo VR) and were sexually harassed within hours of using the platforms, with video clip recordings of the incidents to prove their experiences. One researcher said that when reporting the incident to Horizon Worlds moderators, the moderators stated no guideline infringements occurred and that the user was at fault for not toggling on their personal safety features. The findings of this research are further substantiated by a study conducted by the Center for Countering Digital Hate (2021), which found that users (including children) "are exposed to abusive behaviour every seven minutes" on the VRChat platform.

The repercussions issued by VR gaming companies for harassment in online environments are the same as harassment measures on social media: suspension and banning from the platform. Europol (2022) remarked that there will come a point in time when policy and

lawmakers will have to decide that experiencing harassment and ‘virtual rape’ within the metaverse is ‘equally impactful as those of the physical realm’. A discussed solution to such is the legal personas of avatars within the metaverse; whereby users are held responsible for their avatar’s actions, or at the bare minimum a differentiation is established between the avatar and the legal person behind the avatar (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). The same study also stated that policymakers may further initiatives ‘so that online platforms and law enforcement authorities are better able to identify and respond to dangerous or illicit content’ within the metaverse.

4.2.2 Privacy and Surveillance Issues

The most prominent issue discussed within the realm of VR usage in media and entertainment is the implications on user privacy and surveillance. VR technology carries the same data concerns that are present within traditional social media and internet, and then some. Both VR hardware developers (i.e. Meta, Microsoft) and VR software/application developers (Roblox) have access to data from hardware microphones, cameras, motion-tracking sensors, haptic sensors, which creates graver privacy issues. In addition, there are potential risks of unauthorised access to data gathered by XR devices. For instance, if VR hardware is hacked, an attacker can obtain information about the victim’s physical environment via built-in cameras and sensors, their conversations via built-in microphones, their biometric data etc. (O’Brolcháin et al., 2016). With widespread information leaks and hacks that have previously occurred globally (Wakefield, 2014), hackers could obtain even more information from XR hardware if a similar attack occurred today. XR used for media and entertainment purposes also presents new challenges in well-being, human dignity, and human rights (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). For instance, the emergence of deep fakes in recent years has been a major concern for society.

A study conducted by the University of California Berkeley found that 55,541 VR users could be identified across multiple sessions from their head and hand motions relative to virtual objects (Nair et al., 2023). The researchers state that this data is equivalent to other biometric data (fingerprints, facial recognition), with some users being identified within 2 seconds purely from hand or head movements. The collection of these and other biometric data from XR devices (i.e., eye movement, voice, etc.) presents the possibility of creating a digital replica of a person, making them appear to say and do things which they have not in the real world. These replicas, or deepfakes, can be used for various reasons, like blackmail, social engineering, or other malicious reasons. Such risks may be increased by recent developments in AI technology ([Microsoft’s ‘VALL-E’](#)), which have made it possible to simulate a person’s voice from only 3 second’s worth of audio. In the near future, this combination of AI with VR-collected sensitive data can make social engineering attacks far more convincing.

The adult entertainment industry’s usage of XR has presented similar concerns and issues. Researchers in 2020 found that 100,000 fake nude computer-generated images online of women were non-consensual and made without their knowledge (US Department of Homeland Security, 2021). Through the biometric data collected with XR hardware, it is possible to create deepfakes for non-consensual pornographic content (Mak, 2023). According to Mak (2023), the motion-tracking done by VR headsets can make deepfake creation very effective. According to Kendja (2021), 95% of all deepfakes on the internet are pornographic, with revenge porn being a subset of such content. An English woman discovered that deepfake pornographic content had been made of her without her consent and was circulated on the internet (Kendja, 2021).

Fig. 4.1. Stills of a TikTok deepfake video of the actor Tom Cruise, which attracted the attention of the US Government due to its uncomfortable likeness to real life. (Source: [ABC News Australia, 2021](#)).

The privacy and data concerns with XR hardware are further compounded when an individual uses specific haptic sensors on other sensitive areas of the body, providing more biometric data beyond head and hand movements. Such developments have already been created by researchers at the University of California Berkeley and the Technische Universität München (2022), named 'MetaGuard' (Nair et al., 2022). The plugin essentially adds noise to VR tracking measurements, using an anonymization method called 'differential privacy' to distort the information so that it is no longer precise enough to identify users, without hindering user experience. However, shortly after the launch of the MetaGuard prototype, Metaverse platform VRChat banned the use of this plugin on its platform (Kim, 2022). Platform providers can argue that the use of such plugins can provide users with malicious intent anonymity, making the flagging and reporting process difficult to be successfully done. For privacy and surveillance policy debate in relation to XR technology to make a meaningful development, the debate surrounding the usage and innovations of AI security and anti-surveillance technologies in VR should involve both AI developers and VR Metaverse platform providers, as both have valid arguments for their perspectives but must come to an agreement to solve this major challenge which essentially hinders growth of the sector.

5 Applications in Work and Production Processes

5.1 Overview and State-of-Art

XR technology offers significant potential in the field of work and production across the private sector. Currently, immersive appliances are being developed and used in several industries to enhance various manufacturing activities, such as product design, assembly, maintenance, repair, and training (Ong et al., 2008). XR has been shown to have significant benefits in areas such as machine maintenance and worker training. For example, evidence from Plakas et al. (2020) suggests that the cost of maintaining industrial machinery can be reduced by up to 30% through the use of AR systems. Similarly, research shows that XR enables manufacturers to (re-)train workers at lower cost and with little or no safety risk (Doolani et al., 2020; European Commission et al., 2022; US Government Accountability Office, 2022).

However, beyond the obvious benefits in terms of cost efficiency, there has been less conversion on the utility of immersive training for all workplaces, or the associated data governance challenges of XR devices. As a report by PwC (PwC, 2020) explains, VR platforms offer a new training modality, but may not be suitable to support every type of skills development due to different training objectives, competencies, and collaboration needs.

5.2 Challenges and Limitations

5.2.1 Impact on the Workforce

The introduction of XR into work and production processes has several implications for the workforce. Workers will need training to acquire and update the skills and knowledge needed to use these digital tools (European Commission et al., 2022; US Government, 2022). Current workers may resist change, especially those not used to working with digital technologies. It may also become an issue for job seekers, as XR skills may become a standard requirement for some jobs, thus disadvantaging candidates who have not been exposed to these technologies for economic reasons (Egliston and Carter, 2021) or people with certain disabilities (affecting vision, hearing, mobility, motor skills or cognition) for whom mainstream XR devices may not be fully adapted (Funka et al., 2021).

Employers and the education system need to create the conditions for the development of this digital literacy within the workforce. Stakeholders have identified the need for the European XR ecosystem to “keep promoting relevant skills, in terms of education, training and professional development, as the fast-paced growth of these technologies, combined with their relative novelty in many sectors, may generate an equally rapid skills gap that could widen if left unaddressed.” (European Commission et al., 2022).

5.2.2 Privacy and Security Issues

Data protection issues have been identified as a major concern for manufacturing industries using XR due to the large amount of data collected by XR devices. This provides employers with a wide range of personal information about employees that can be used for a variety of purposes, many of which can be considered intrusive. One of these uses is the monitoring of employees in the workplace (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). As noted by the Rathenau Instituut (2020), this “raises concerns about the privacy and autonomy of employees and the extent to which they can consent to the use of technology and have control over its use”. XR can be included in the category of ‘wearable devices’, characterised by the Article 29 Working Party (European Commission, Directorate General Justice and Consumers, 2017) as ‘intrusive and pervasive forms of surveillance’ in the workplace.

Another application of XR technologies in the workplace is the evaluation of employee performance based on biometric data generated by XR devices. This poses two problems. First, employees need to be properly informed that their data will be used for such purposes and give their explicit consent in accordance with the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). However, in an employment relationship characterised by an imbalance of power, consent may not be the appropriate legal basis, as “it is unlikely that the data subject is able to deny his/her employer consent to data processing without experiencing the fear or real risk of detrimental effects as a result of a refusal.” (ECJ, 2018, p. 29). Furthermore, this type of purpose may be considered as automated decision making, which is problematic not only from a data protection perspective, but also for workers’ rights, as it may lead to “inequalities in processes such as hiring, performance evaluation and training.” (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022, p. 5). One solution proposed by PwC (2020) for delivering VR training in the workplace is to take organisational and

technical measures to make the data anonymous at source, so that no specific person can be identified.

Cybersecurity issues are also a concern when using XR in manufacturing processes, especially as there is an additional risk of vulnerabilities that may impact the production process (US Government, 2022). Security on XR technologies must be focused both in the operating system and the application running in the device (PwC, 2020). Data breaches may have obvious consequences for the employees using the device as previously analysed, but also to the company, since confidential information of the company and corporate secrets can be exposed (Rathenau Instituut, 2022).

6 Applications in Medical Processes and Health Care

6.1 Overview and State-of-Art

In the healthcare sector, XR has been a fixture for some time and is used in numerous areas. XR tools are not only used for training by medical professionals and students, but also for diagnosis and surgical treatment of various diseases (European Commission, 2022). Simultaneously, there are numerous applications used by patients or the general population, e.g., patient and caregiver education, pain management, treatment and therapies, assistance or rehabilitation (European Commission, 2022).

Probably the largest part of this is the application of XR in psychology. In psychological research, XR, specifically VR, has become an integral part of the research tool repertoire. Studies have shown that VR can provide a controlled and immersive environment for studying human behaviour, emotions, and cognition alongside the “classic” psychological laboratory experiments (Andreatta et al., 2023). Here, psychological VR-based research not only focuses on general psychological phenomena but is also increasingly used to study mental illnesses and their therapeutic options (Bell et al., 2020; Riva, 2005; Valmaggia, Day, et al., 2016).

In this context, VR has shown promising results as a treatment for a variety of disorders, especially anxiety disorders which are the most prevalent mental disorder to date (Eaton et al., 2018; Jacobi et al., 2004; Pereira et al., 2020; Wittchen et al., 2011). For example, exposure therapy is used to treat specific phobias¹ as part of psychotherapeutic treatment and is currently considered the most effective method in its treatment (Böhnlein et al., 2020; Choy et al., 2007). For this purpose, affected individuals are gradually confronted with the fearful stimulus in a controlled setting to disprove anxiety beliefs, which ultimately leads to a reduction of fear (Böhnlein et al., 2020; Choy et al., 2007; Neudeck, 2015; Teismann & Margraf, 2018). With assistance of virtual exposure therapy (VRET), this therapeutic intervention is transferred into the virtual space (Botella et al., 2017; Rothbaum et al., 1997). Studies and meta-analyses have shown that VRET is equivalent or even superior to in vivo exposure therapy in terms of effect sizes (Botella et al., 2017; Rothbaum et al., 2006; Valmaggia, Latif, et al., 2016). As a result, VR(ET) is finding broader application in psychological research and is now even being offered commercially as a therapeutic alternative for phobias paid for by the statutory health insurance (see for instance <https://invirto.de/>).

Currently, not only VR, but also AR, is mainly used in the field of anxiety disorders or anxiety-associated disorders such as PTSD. However, these technologies are also applied in the

investigation of addictive disorders and eating disorders. Nevertheless, studies in these areas often focus on the investigation of causal and disease-maintaining factors. AR und augmented reality exposure therapy (ARET), too, has grown in popularity with the improved accessibility of corresponding devices (De Witte et al., 2020). As a result, XR now also has an established position in fundamental psychological research. For example, conditioning studies conducted to research anxiety disorders are increasingly being shifted into virtual space.

Translational studies to test animal models used for the development of psychopharmaceuticals are also carried out in VR for economic reasons and thus boost interdisciplinary research to gain a profound understanding of mental disorders (see Madeira et al., 2021 for an example). In addition, XR is utilized to observe the effects of medication on a human sample in a practical and “non-laboratory” environment (Mühlberger et al., 2020). Finally, a significant body of research deals with the psychological effects of XR itself. This not only covers effects like simulator sickness but also trust and/or acceptance of virtual avatars. In this context, ethics of XR use are also up for a vivid debate.

In the medical field, XR has been used since the 1990s, especially in the surgical field for training, surgery planning and even intraoperative guidance (Sadeghi et al., 2022; Sugimoto, 2021). In addition, medical students as well as nursing students also benefit from a virtual representation of human anatomy as well as a vivid illustration of physiological processes. Consequently, XR mainly ranks high here in the field of (continuing) education and skills training. In addition, in the course of detailed imaging of the human body, it is now also possible to use XR for the diagnosis of diseases, especially for the distinction of cancerous tissue (European Commission: Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology & Visionary Analytics., 2023; Pareek et al., 2018). In addition, in the diagnostic field, XR can also be used to visualize minor vascular abnormalities or even protein activity (European Commission: Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology & Visionary Analytics., 2023).

Figure 6.2. Clinical and surgical application of XR in cardiothoracic surgery (Sadeghi et al., 2022)

Newer fields of application can also be found in the area of (neurological) rehabilitation. For example, XR is used here to help patients with movement restrictions after a stroke to restore the mobility of the impacted limbs and is considered to be even more effective than traditional rehabilitation programs in some studies (Arlati & Borghetti, 2022; Howard, 2017; H. S. Lee et al., 2019). What has to be kept in mind though, is that recipients of XR-based rehabilitation programs are often elderly. However, XR tools are often oriented towards a younger population and are rarely adapted to the needs of older people (Chen, 2020; Nanda et al., 2022). This addresses both physical, e.g., eyesight, and mental deficits, i.e., cognitive impairment but also the lack of technological literacy (L. N. Lee et al., 2019). The acceptance rates in older adults are high if they are introduced into the technology in a guided manner and can serve as a motivating factor to promote wellbeing (Appel et al., 2020; Huygelier et al., 2019; L. N. Lee et al., 2019).

Furthermore, XR has been found a very effective tool in the treatment of chronic and acute pain (Ahmadpour et al., 2019; Pourmand et al., 2018). This circumstance is also remarkable because the pharmaceutical-based treatment of pain is often accompanied by numerous side effects. XR offers, according to some studies, a similarly effective treatment option, which is now also affordable and thus represents a serious treatment alternative (Bordeleau et al., 2022).

6.2 Challenges and Limitations

In general, the advantages of using XR in the psychological and medical area manifest themselves primarily in the economy of application, the controllability of the situation and the adaptability to the needs of patients, therapists and the medical staff alike. Nevertheless, the use of XR is not only associated with advantages. Central concerns relate both to "trivial" issues such as the disinfection of VR equipment, especially in a hospital context, and more so to the fear that sensitive patient data may not be protected in accordance with the applicable legislation (Martingano & Persky, 2021). This is particularly problematic in view of the fact that the unique identification of users is easily possible through the tracking data provided (Nair et al., 2023). Consequently, it is imperative to develop a mandatory data protection concept for handling such data and, under certain circumstances, to implement it in legislation.

In view of the current market fragmentation of XR applications and devices, the general implementation of legal framework conditions is of particular importance (European Commission: Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology & Visionary Analytics., 2023). This issue will gain even more attraction with regards to the development of the Metaverse. Another problem in the use of XR in the medical and psychological field is simulator sickness. There are several guidelines to reduce the occurrence of e.g., nausea and dizziness. However, it remains unclear to what extent these are always implemented and there is surprisingly still very little research on what "risk factors" exist based on the user (Grassini et al., 2021). Possible correlations have already been found in connection with certain personality traits such as "emotionality," which could be particularly problematic in the context of emotion eliciting XR scenarios (Grassini et al., 2021). In any case, simulator sickness is a common side effect of XR. Therefore, it is essential to consider it when designing XR scenarios.

Another point of concern is the possible psychosocial and medical consequences of XR use in general. The first thing to note here, is that age-related findings are still fragmentary especially when it comes to empirical studies with children or young adults. Although there are already numerous studies on the harmfulness of individual factors, e.g., screen time, in the field of general computer use, which is reflected in the new diagnosis of Internet Gaming Disorder in the DSM-5, there is a paucity in substantiated results on this in the context of XR (Kaimara et al., 2022; Kenwright, 2018; Slater et al., 2020). For instance, it remains plausible that children to some extent will not be capable of differentiating between the virtual and the real world and thus suffer from social impairments (Kenwright, 2018).

The fact that content experienced in VR is taken into the real world can already be derived from embodiment research (Flavián et al., 2021; Kilteni et al., 2012; Reinhard et al., 2020). However, this danger is not only evident for children and adolescents but could also become more significant for adults. This is another reason why the potential for addiction and other health hazards is already being discussed in connection with XR and the Metaverse (Bojic, 2022). It also speaks for itself that manufacturers of XR tools provide their products with a note that they are not suitable for children before a certain age or that a maximum of screen time is advised.

But not only mental health issues are important in this context. Long-lasting physical consequential impairments, such as myopia, have also already been mentioned by experts (Kaimara et al., 2022). In the case of AR in particular, the merging of the real and virtual worlds is evaluated critically in that AR glasses, for example, can be considered such a strong distraction that life-threatening accidents could occur. For example, the speed of cars could be misjudged by AR-using pedestrians, resulting in a collision (Sabelman & Lam, 2015). However, these types of hazards could be prevented through appropriate design solutions (Sabelman & Lam, 2015).

In their article, Slater et al. (2020) further discussed a number of psychological and social consequences of XR. These included social isolation, PTSD as a result of unexpected horror or exposure to violence, but also lack of ground truth. As this paper impressively shows, from a scientific point of view it has to be stated that regulations concerning the (physical and mental) health of XR have been insufficiently addressed so far. Generally speaking, the current status of research on the health effects of XR is far behind the developmental progress of this technology. Consequently, further critical and scientific discussion is absolutely necessary, also with a view to future developments. Although there are already EU-wide approaches to regulate (Medical Devices Regulation), promote (EIT Health) and also regulate the advancing digitalization in the health sector, these surprisingly do not include XR or are not adapted for this technology. Consequently, a glaring regulatory gap must be identified here, which can be closed through interdisciplinary scientific discourse (European Commission: Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology & Visionary Analytics., 2023).

7 Application in Marketing and Trade

7.1 Overview and State-of-Art

XR technologies offer interesting opportunities in the field of marketing and trade, especially for retailers. The use of XR would be an advantage for both sellers, as consumers are "keener and even delighted to be interacting with promotional content as it 'comes to life'." (XRAA, n/d), and consumers, since customer service may be improved through a virtual environment (ITAS, 2019). In addition, companies can save resources by reducing the need for samples and inventory (EUIPO, 2020).

One of the main applications being currently used by advertisers is the participation of customers in "experience marketing", i.e., the simulation of offered goods by users in a recognisable context (e.g., their homes) before a purchase is made (Mhaidli & Schaub, 2021; XRAA, 2023). Such a feature is usually provided by the 3D model of products projected into the real environment through AR devices. Several retailers (as Ikea) and clothing companies have created applications of this type (ITAS, 2019), while other companies take advantage of the AR features of social media networks (as Instagram or Snapchat filters) to promote their products and services (Forbes Agency Council, 2017). AR applications are also being used as a complement in physical stores to increase customer engagement with the products on offer. However, the next step for advertisers is to move the product presentation entirely to virtual environments, in the form of virtual shops and department stores where customers can go shopping through their VR devices (ITAS, 2019).

Even the tourism industry, which is based on physical experiences, has engaged in XR advertisement to show travel destinations 'as vividly as possible' through XR devices (ITAS, 2019). Studies suggest that the use of VR headsets to experience a travel destination led to positive outcomes, generating enhanced interest and intentions to visit the place in potential tourists (Tussyadiah et al., 2018).

7.2 Challenges and Limitations

7.2.1 Privacy Issues

As in many other sectors, privacy is one of the key issues identified in both academic papers (Hoffman et al., 2022; Wedel et al., 2020) and stakeholder reports (BPC, 2022) on the use of XR in advertising. These concerns are driven by the fact that XR technologies allow advertisers to collect a greater amount of personal data from consumers, including biometric data (Hoffman et

al., 2022) (Egliston and Carter, 2021). This data can be used to improve the measurement and effectiveness of their metrics, including customer personalisation, engagement, and behaviour (cf. PwC, 2020). In fact, data collection through XR devices allows advertisers to obtain information that was not available through other forms of marketing (Hoffman et al., 2022). For example, Feng & Mueller (2019, p. 454) point out that “it’s hard to measure the effectiveness of a television ad or a billboard. However, with AR, marketers can track just how many people engaged with a particular ad, and even for how long”.

The privacy implications of XR advertising also extend to data subjects other than the targeted consumer, given the ability of these technologies to collect information from the user’s physical environment, which includes both private and public spaces (Snijders et al., 2020). This was one of the main reasons why Google Glasses was discontinued (De Ruyter et al., 2020). The impact on public spaces is not only related to the data collected, but also to the display of customised advertising on XR devices, which could tailor the reality by blocking or filtering the people or things that the customer prefers to avoid based on their profile (Snijders et al., 2020) or even cause an overload of the digital public space (ITA, 2022).

As mentioned above, the large amount of data collected by XR technologies can give advertisers access to customers’ biometric data (Wedel et al., 2020; XRAA, 2023), which, as a specific category of data, enjoys enhanced protection under the GDPR and requires a specific consent given by the data subjects (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). Even if these data are currently mostly collected through VR devices (Wedel et al., 2020), AR technologies are increasingly adopting new functionalities that fall under this category, such as gesture recognition or voice activation (De Ruyter et al., 2020). This trend may also raise a new level of concern, given that AR technologies may, in the near future, give advertisers access to a wide range of neurophysiological signals (Wedel et al., 2020).

The European Parliamentary Research Service (2022) has warned that the processing of biometric data can lead to intrusive profiling “which could have harmful consequences, such as loss of control over one’s life and decisions”. These warnings are particularly important when it comes to XR advertising, given that advertisers may have a new power to persuade their consumers (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022; Snijders et al., 2020) and even lead to emotional manipulation by tailoring the content of such ads. Mhaidli and Schaub (2021, p. 11) say that “XR ads can be created that simulate individuals who have significant emotional sway over a consumer (e.g., a trusted figure, or a figure the consumer has affection for).”

In line with the principle of ‘privacy by design’ embedded in the European data protection framework, stakeholders have proposed to incorporate privacy compliance in the development of XR technologies. These technical measures include data anonymization (e.g., facial blurring) and minimization, public-private location demarcation (known as geofencing), and effective definition and request of consent, among others (BPC, 2022; De Ruyter et al., 2020).

7.2.2 Consumer Rights

As previously described, the growing databases collected by advertisers through XR devices could have a major impact on individuals, as their intimacy can be exposed and used for manipulation purposes. Such an issue has implications not only for their rights as data subjects, but also as consumers. People targeted by XR ads may have false expectations of 3D representations of products, as the “previewed products will not be the actual products, but rather, digital recreations of them.” (Mhaidli & Schaub, 2021). In fact, it is highly likely that virtual models will differ from the products in size, colour, or even special placement (Wedel et al., 2020) and even look better than the real thing (EUIPO, 2020). This misleading “experience marketing” may be accidental due to technical limitations of XR technologies, but it may also be provoked to take

advantage of consumers (Mhaidli & Schaub, 2021). These cases may require further guidelines from consumer protection authorities for XR advertising. Finally, consumers could also be targeted by criminals impersonating businesses in XR environments (e.g., setting up fake virtual stores) in order to extract personal information or bank details (phishing) (Europol, 2022).

7.2.3 Intellectual Property and Competition Issues

The use of XR technologies in advertising can have an impact not only on consumers, but also on the companies using them and their competitors. One such impact is on intellectual property (IP). Not surprisingly, the digital environment has made it easier to reproduce copyrighted works, trademarks, and other protected assets without the permission of their owners, and XR technologies are no exception. Stakeholders are concerned that IP assets can be easily manipulated and copied in AR or VR environments (EUIPO, 2020). For example, an AR app can replace a brand with a digitally generated competitor's trademark or even trigger prejudicial content (Marcinoska-Boulangé, 2017). The immersive nature of XR also challenges the ability to properly enforce these IP rights, as such content can be "distributed and replicated across decentralised networks running on Web 3.0 and blockchain-based platforms" (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). Although there are no XR cases in the European courts, the case law of the European Court of Justice (ECJ) (in particular Case C-323/09 *Interflora v Marks & Spencer*) may provide guidance for future cases of trademark infringement in an XR environment (Marcinoska-Boulangé, 2017).

Another related issue is the potential for unfair practices in the use of XR advertising. For example, an AR application may trigger content that damages the reputation of competitors by targeting their products or brands or by highlighting its own products. This risk may also be increased if the provider of the XR technology is also the provider of the favoured products (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022). In the European context, the German competition authority (Bundeskartellamt) has already found that Meta (formerly Facebook) has a dominant position in the virtual market due to its use of data gathered by Facebook accounts on its Oculus headsets (Egliston and Carter, 2021). As a result, Facebook announced Meta accounts, allowing its VR users not to use a Facebook account.

Reducing the various risks posed by online advertising is one of the objectives of the Digital Services Act (DSA), which extends the regime for dealing with illegal or potentially harmful content by online platforms, including XR providers (Considerati, 2021). The DSA imposes transparency obligations on advertising and encourages the development of codes of conduct to tackle competition and data protection breaches.

8 Applications in Security

8.1 Overview and State-of-Art

The field of application in the security sector includes not only the (obvious) military sector but also police work, disaster control and the simulation of rescue operations (Kind et al., 2019). Training applications in particular occupy a large space in all areas. For example, various military institutions use VR in particular to train prospective soldiers for their deployment. The training simulates not only simple combat situations but is also used to consolidate certain skills such as parachuting or situational awareness (Kind et al., 2019). Here, the advantages are apparent. Simulation with the help of XR can provide the ideal preparation for future combat operations without the need for (significantly) riskier "on the job" training (if at all possible). For this purpose, high-risk operations can also be simulated in various degrees of severity as well as substantial

equipment training (Lele, 2013; Mao & Chen, 2020), thus offering the possibility to provide training across different departments and operating ranges. This also includes flight simulators, which have long been part of the civil aerospace industry already.

In the context of military deployment, VR is also used to process the consequences of deployment, such as stress and even PTSD. As previously mentioned in the Medical Applications section, VR is already successfully used in the treatment of some mental disorders. Used in acute conditions, VR applications offer an effective way to relieve stress as well as reduce negative affect and thus offer a potentially preventive effect (Hyun et al., 2022; Pallavicini et al., 2016; Rizzo et al., 2011). Moreover, the potential that XR can have on the battlefield was identified and realized in the context of AR-based interfaces that would support combat by for instance marking enemy positions (Argenta et al., 2010; Kenny, 2015; Roberts et al., 2012). Enabling medical care for combat casualties can even be provided by such XR solutions. For example, Leuze et al. (2021) developed AR software that would enable medical personnel to access the individual anatomic conditions of soldiers to provide medical assistance in an emergency. In summary, it can be said that XR is used in many military areas, even if detailed studies on this, probably also due to the security law basis, are not publicly accessible.

Law enforcement agencies are now also using XR for training (see Hurst, 2023 for an example). Here, too, the focus is largely on training procedures that are intended to prepare future police officers in dealing with confusing and highly stressful situations (Caserman et al., 2018; Giessing, 2021). In this field, studies have shown that VR-based training is remarkably similar to real-world situations and thus provides a good foundation (Kleygrewe et al., 2023). One area for XR that is now growing in importance concerns the so-called smart policing. Police forces primarily use AR to obtain real-time information during police operations, for example, for traffic control or suspect identification (Bang et al., 2019; Gong et al., 2017; Haque & Saleem, 2020).

In addition, institutions dealing with disaster and civil protection can also benefit from training measures that can be realized through XR (Egger-Lampl et al., 2022; Hsu et al., 2013). In their review, Khanal et al. (2022) analysed papers from 2009 to 2019 and discovered that XR technologies have a definite place in disaster management forces in various areas. Newer approaches prefer to combine multiple technologies, such as drones and XR, to intervene even faster and, most importantly, with less risk (Velev et al., 2019).

8.2 Challenges and Limits

XR has already established itself as an important technology in both the military and civilian sectors. As in the other application areas, however, there are various limitations that must be considered. The greatest concerns about the widespread use of XR are essentially data protection issues (Snijders et al., 2022). Especially security and military actions are often subject to classification for the protection of the involved parties as well as the protection of national interests. Since data protection in relation to XR has generally been rather inadequately regulated to date, there is definitely a risk that sensitive information could be extracted and thus military (classified) operations could be uncovered by for instance, leaked base location.

Data protection concerns also exist in the context of smart policing, especially on the part of society. Furthermore, data protectionists point to the abolition of data protection if every citizen can become the target of possibly warrantless police surveillance at any time (Neely, 2019; Spiegel, 2018). Likewise, the proportionality in the sense of ethical considerations of XR in the police context is called for in general (Afzal & Panagiotopoulos, 2022). Simultaneously, it must be noted that with a view to future technical developments, the police and legal discussion of XR is necessary. This is one

of the reasons why Interpol provided a virtual Metaverse version of its headquarters in Lyon for training purposes (Interpol, 2022).

Fig 8.1.: Interpol's metaverse (Source: Interpol, 2022)

Furthermore, design implications for the permanent wearing of XR tools are currently still critical. It must be considered here that soldiers, police officers or even first responders could find themselves in critical and potentially life-threatening situations while simultaneously wearing AR glasses. Consequently, it must be ensured that typical side effects such as nausea do not occur at any time. That this is not always the case is shown by a report from the US Army, according to which soldiers reported symptoms of physical impairment while using HoloLens-based AR headsets for a longer time (Harding, 2022). Additionally, (and as previously mentioned), the headsets are usually found in the gaming context and are also adapted accordingly. Consequently, this means that they are not necessarily customized for the needs of the military and police. For example, the US Army reported that the headset's reflections can be seen from far away and thus reveal the user's position (Harding, 2022). It also seems questionable whether the devices are stable for long-term use under difficult conditions. This also includes the non-trivial possibility that users could become disoriented and thus more vulnerable in the event of a sudden system failure, e.g., due to damage.

In summary, it can be said that XR has great potential for the security sector and is already being used extensively here. Nevertheless, general problems such as data security and design decisions also affect the use of XR tools in security-relevant areas. Consequently, further research and policy recommendations are of central importance here as well.

9 Applications in Education

9.1 Overview and State-of-Art

There is a considerable overlap in technologies and uses of XR between education, work, and production. To avoid this overlap, this section will solely focus on the current applications of XR

in education and the debates in the education and research fields surrounding such applications, and not in the training work environment.

9.1.1 XR in Medical and STEM Education

The most widespread applications of XR in education is within the medical education sector, with hardware such as the Microsoft HoloLens being used in classroom settings to allow students to experience complex medical procedures without having to enter an operating theatre or partake in high-risk operations on real patients. An example of such is the 'AugMedicine' AR app developed by Leiden University Medical Centre (see article by Jelger & LUMC, 2019), which gives students insights into the 'postoperative anatomy of kidney and pancreatic transplant patients' (see Fig. 9.1. below). The technology incorporates 2D CT scan images alongside 3D anatomical models of organs so students gain a better understanding of spatial relations between CT scans and what that may look like on actual organs.

The benefits to such technology in medical education are two-fold: better interpretation of CT scan imagery and making the teaching of such complex operational procedures easier and less risky. Similar applications of XR in medical education include the [University of California San Francisco's](#) use of XR to 'practice dynamically removing layers of tissue and organ systems.'

Another side to medical education is the patient care subsection, in which XR can be used to simulate scenarios with patients with conditions such as dementia. A VR experience developed by the Leiden University Centre for Innovation and the Elderly Care Physician training program (named 'Behaviour: (not) an issue') (Leiden University - Centre of Innovation, 2019) provides students with an 'insight into behavioural symptoms of patients with dementia. Multiple scenarios are built into the role-play experience, helping students to gain better practical understandings of the ins-and-outs of the daily lives of dementia patients.

Fig 9.1. 'AugMedicine' AR app [Leiden University Medical Centre](#) (2019)

The training of students with VR technology allows them to engage in problematic situations that would not be possible without actually going into a care home and interacting with dementia patients. It eliminates the theoretical and textual form of learning about such scenarios, which students and teachers alike think "lacks presence, empathy and connection with reality" (Leiden

University - Centre of Innovation, 2019). Other patient care educational applications of XR include in mental health for PTSD patients, and stroke rehabilitation (XRA, 2021).

Other areas in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) which use XR as a medium of learning include chemistry lab experiments (Leiden University - Centre of Innovation, 2019), and engineers using CAD modeling without incurring costs on labour, materials etc.

9.1.2 XR in Humanities

The use of XR technology for language learning can be beneficial to students by making an immersive experience in a virtual world, where they can practice their target language with other users. According to [XR ERA](#) (see article by Ji, 2020), this makes language learning more accessible as it removes time and financial constraints which stand in the way of students becoming immersed in their target language by going to the country of the language. XR in language learning allows the experience to be more affective, social, and practical than what traditional classroom settings provide.

Similarly, in historical and archaeological studies, XR technology may be used to immerse students in virtual worlds of the past, which would not be possible in traditional learning methods. A collaboration between 4D Research Lab, TU Delft and SURF saw the virtual reconstruction of the old Vlooienburg neighbourhood of Amsterdam (Sanchez & Schipper, 2021). Such virtual environments of locations that existed in a different era of history immerses students into the topic further, making them more memorable to learn.

9.1.3 XR for Students with Disabilities

XR can be applied in educational settings for those with mental and physical disabilities to provide them with learning experiences catered to their needs and better inclusion (European Commission: Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology & Visionary Analytics., 2023). People with physical disabilities can improve their physical education and experience learning activities which their conditions may have hindered them from engaging in, such as field trips (European Commission, 2023). Ke and Lee (2016) conducted a study whereby two students with high-functioning autism (HFA) were paired with a non-autistic peer for five weeks in a project on architectural design. They found that VR-based collaboration on the design project “awarded children with HFA an opportunity to practice and develop flexibility, identity, and norm construction” (Ke & Lee, 2016, p. 1511). Examples of current XR applications in education for those with mental disabilities and neurodivergence include ‘CoMove’ (Zhang et al., 2018), which aims to improve meaningful factors of verbal communication and collaboration.

9.2 Challenges and Limitations

While the value added by XR technologies in education is widely recognised, there are some elements of the technologies’ application which are debated within academia. The most obvious issue being the data and privacy concerns. Similar to data protection issues within work and production applications, the usage of XR in education requires the collection of large amounts of students’ data, which teachers/educators have access to that can be utilised in many ways which can be invasive. Teachers may even make assessments using XR technology compulsory to complete courses, thus forcing students to reveal sensitive information they (or their parents in the case of underage children) may not want to share (European Commission, 2023).

General aims of data protection regulation apply to XR applications and hardware, but there is a lack of instruments to deal with XR-specific issues, such as the specific requirements to process biometric data (European Commission, 2023). Without clear guidance from European regulators, full

GDPR compliance may become an obstacle for the XR usage in education. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic in Germany, the strictness of European regulations resulted in barriers for the implementation of virtual meeting platforms. As a result, German teachers' ability to connect with students was disrupted, causing a "huge gap in knowledge transfer" (XR World Association, n.d.; European Commission, 2023). Stakeholders within the education and research sectors, mostly teachers and their institutions, have stated that constant updates required for ensuring user data and privacy protection are overwhelming to some, especially those who are not (very) technologically literate (SURF, 2023). A proposed solution to such is to take an acceptance approach (SURF, 2023), and to develop standards on how XR applications are to be used within the institution with revisions for any legal/technological advancements (Rui, 2022).

Educational institutions must ensure that when they invest in technology, that it is put to the best use possible. When used correctly, XR may enhance the learning experiences of students beyond what would be possible without its utilisation of XR in their learning methods. However, under or over usage of XR technology in lessons could be counterproductive to the learning process of the students (Logeswaran et al., 2021). Another significant issue is the affordability of XR technology. XR hardware comes at a high financial cost, which educational institutions would have to buy multiples of in order for students to have equal and fair learning opportunities. Logeswaran et al. (2021) suggest that a learner-centred approach to using extended reality in healthcare education could be the most successful method of causing a paradigm shift within the field. Inequality in financial capabilities and attitudes fuelled by teachers' fear of change are cited as compounding factors in lower XR applications in education (Bucea-Manea-Țoniș et al., 2020; European Commission et al., 2022). These factors would seem to explain why the adoption of XR is lower in Eastern European countries when compared to the rest of Europe (Van Kessel et al., 2022).

XR applications in education for those with disabilities also present challenges. Persons with mental disabilities can be overwhelmed by sudden changes in environmental and specific sensory experiences, which XR technologies may trigger due to their immersive nature (European Commission, 2023). There may also be barriers in abilities to use XR devices and applications, as some persons with disabilities have lower digital skills and their disabilities may hinder their opportunities to engage with such technology, for example in the cases of restricted sight, hearing, and epilepsy (European Commission, 2023). Individuals of a vulnerable background may also not be able to give informed consent in cases of limited decision-making abilities or circumstances, which can be a data and privacy risk. These challenges must be carefully accounted for in the application of XR in educating persons with disabilities so that learning potentials are maximised, and harm is minimised.

10 Applications in Urban Planning and Conservation

Undoubtedly today, the advancements within XR on its hardware and software side helps us in the representation and interpretation of reality, present and past, having become a powerful tool supporting social sciences and humanities, various fields and domains including urban planning, and conservation. The digital 3D representation of reality around us in the urban setting has opened a world of possibilities—possibilities which grow each day with the emergence of new challenges and opportunities (Ioannides et al., 2017).

10.1 Overview and State-of-Art

Many cities have 3D models of their aboveground infrastructure so called digital twins; buildings, transportation networks, parks, and other infrastructure typically captured in 2D or 3D imagery from

overflights or in 2D GIS maps. Imagery is not very smart and extracting 3D vector objects such as building footprints, heights, profiles and transportation networks requires sophisticated post-processing. Even more importantly, underground infrastructure is usually neglected, even though it is recognized that water and wastewater, energy (gas, electric power, and district heating), and communications (fibre and copper) networks provide the life blood of the city and over.

Rotterdam has been developing its 3D model, which underpins the digital twin, for several years. This contains street furniture such as streetlights, trees and underground parts of street furniture, a large-scale base-map, a complete map of underground networks of cables and pipes, buildings, and non-physical content such as zoning regulations and bylaws. The 3D model is kept in sync with data repositories maintained by city departments and others. In the future it will also include real-time data streams from a variety of sensors.

Instead of relying on proprietary solutions and services the 3D model is open, based on open standards and many of the applications that have been developed for it, as open-source projects. Moreover, visualizations rely on Cesium, an open-source initiative which has just [announced](#) support for visualizing underground utilities, mines, and geological layers (Shehata, 2020). The rationale for the data being based on open standards is that a standards-based environment creates an open data commons where developers can devote their time to developing innovative applications rather than spending time converting data from one format to another.

Furthermore, the implementation of open standards and open data also enables cities to share data among them. For instance, the Dutch Kadaster has developed an open 3D map of the whole of the Netherlands ([Nederland in 3D, n.d](#)) with scales ranging from 1:500 to 1:25,000 in collaboration with academic, private sector, and public sector partners. All data in the 3D map is built on the basis of open standards. The map was created by combining existing 2D data with the Elevation Model of the Netherlands resulting from a LiDAR survey which covers the whole of the Netherlands with a resolution of eight elevation points per square meter.

Open data and open standards also relate to a critical issue that is of growing importance: many governments have adopted transparency and open data as a cornerstone of democratic policy. On the other hand, often, digital twins for smart cities are being developed by private-sector firms or by public-private initiatives.

Digital Twins require the interplay of various components for data collection, processing, communication, modelling, analytics simulation and control. Some of these specific steps can be distributed, which leads to a need to take a system-of-system approach to characterize and manage these subsystems to ensure cross-disciplinary interoperability and maintain the credibility of digital twins. The ISO-23247 provides a generic digital twin development framework to help manufacturers choose building blocks for digital twin implementation. This standard can help analyse digital twins project requirements and use common terminologies between stakeholders within the project cycle.

Since the digital twin concept is still in its early stage, there are not many standards specifically developed for digital twins. A recently developed International Organization for Standardization (ISO)/Draft International Standard (DIS), ISO 23247, Digital Twin Manufacturing Framework, is one of such standards. However, existing standards for data collection, data security, information modelling, system modelling, simulation, visualization, and networking, which have been developed for generic or specific purposes, can also support digital twin applications.

Standards can serve as force multipliers for the digital transformation. Enabling context-dependent instantiations, composability, interoperability, and reusability of its components. Standards would also

support other requirements such as digital thread, data synchronization, data assurance and data security, and user interfaces. Voluntary, consensus-based standards provide transparency and critical guidance in the methods for developing, deploying, structuring, and using digital twins in manufacturing. The following standards are noted because of their relevance to the digital twin concept. These standards are developed for modelling of digital twins in manufacturing or digital factories and should not be regarded a complete list (Shao, 2021):

- IEC TS (The International Electrotechnical Commission Technical Specifications) 62832, Digital Factory Framework. The specification defines a framework to establish and maintain the digital representation of a production system throughout its life cycle. A consistent exchange of information between all processes and partners related to a production system can be achieved by the support of the framework. Information, therefore, can become understandable, reusable, and changeable through the entire production system life cycle.
- IEEE (The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) P2806, System Architecture of Digital Representation for Physical Objects in Factory Environments. The standard supports the creation of digital factories. It describes the objective, components, data sources required, and procedure of digital representation in factory environments
- IPC (The Institute for Interconnecting and Packaging Electronic Circuits) 2551, International Standard for Digital Twins. The standard is part of the IPC Factory of the Future standards. The IPC digital twin is comprised of the digital twin product, manufacturing process, and lifecycle frameworks. Within the digital twin architecture, the standard stipulates and defines digital twin properties, types, complexities, and readiness levels. It also includes historical information about a product, including the history of design in terms of revision and engineering changes, and manufacturing information (i.e., digital thread).
- DIN SPEC, the Asset Administration Shell (AAS). AAS describes an asset electronically in a standardized manner. Its purpose is to exchange assets related data among industrial assets, between assets and production systems or engineering tools. AAS supports implementations of digital twins for industrial applications
- ISO 23247, Digital Twin Framework for Manufacturing. The standard series defines a framework that provides a generic guideline, a reference architecture, methods, and approaches for case-specific, digital-twin implementations. The standard supports the composability of models and interoperability among modules. It also provides examples of data collection, communication, integration, modelling, and applications of relevant standards.

A broader adoption of standards could support the interoperability required to enable this system-of-systems approach (Ken Timsit, 2022). Digital twin standards are still young, and a widespread adoption could play a crucial role in digital transformation for physical industries. Thinking from both a systems-of-systems approach and a lifecycle approach, this can save a lot of effort on the information exchange, by reusing information and data while avoiding customized efforts.

The Augmented Reality for Collaborative Urban Planning project (Artefacto Augmented Reality, n.d), for instance, pursues to improve citizen's understanding of future urban plans by visualising them with location based or augmented reality, by allowing them to provide feedback, and by analysing the results throughout the design phase.

A further approach is that adopted by Open Ireland (openireland.eu). The Open Ireland CONNECT Test bed will take an end-to-end to the network, including wireless, optical and cloud-based research using open interfaces and open source. It will investigate intelligent control plane technology and protocols and enable 100X scalability, exploring issues such as capacity, latency, availability and automation. The testbed includes indoor and outdoor 5G new radio, cloud, and optical transmission equipment deployed within Trinity College Dublin, around the Dublin Docklands area, and out to the DCU Campus in North Dublin. Its key features will include an open networking technology, such as OpenRAN, cloud central office, and disaggregated optical systems; enabling experimentation on AI-based intelligent control mechanisms to provide full network automation and customization; enabling experimentation on network infrastructure sharing across multiple operators and services; involving both indoor and outdoor cells, based on OpenRAN split 7.2; and, using dark fibre connectivity, providing the freedom to carry out any type of transmission experiments, without causing disruption to production networks (see Figure 10.1).

Fig. 10.1. Open Ireland project (openireland.eu)

10.2 Challenges and Limitations

By nature, XR devices have world-facing sensor technology built-in, for example, LiDAR sensing, and directional microphones. This sensing is what, in part, drives the Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithms that allow XR devices to localize and position themselves within their surrounding (where they are in the physical world). These possibilities not only make it possible to visualize digital assets in the physical world, but also open up new potential risks that go beyond positional tracking and risks of the user itself (Nair et al., 2023).

With the recent explosive growth of interest and investment within XR, public attention has rightly shifted toward the unique security and privacy threats that these platforms and output devices may pose. While it has long been known that people reveal information about themselves via their motion, the extent to which this makes an individual globally identifiable within virtual reality has not yet been widely understood. In the research paper Unique Identification of 50,000+ Virtual Reality Users from Head & Hand Motion Data, it has been shown that large number of real VR users can be uniquely and reliably identified across multiple sessions using just their head and hand motion

relative to virtual objects. After training a classification model on 5 minutes of data per person, a user can be uniquely identified amongst the entire pool of 50,000+ with 94.33% accuracy from 100 seconds of motion, and with 73.20% accuracy from just 10 seconds of motion. This research has been the first to truly demonstrate the extent to which biomechanics may serve as a unique identifier within XR, on par with widely used biometrics such as facial or fingerprint recognition.

Perhaps the most immediate risk enabled by such sensing is the ability to observe and track bystanders of the XR user. Driven by advances in machine learning and computer vision, an XR device will be able to segment, classify, and track these proximate others. It can be assumed that a device will be able to volumetrically capture the bystander and generate a 3D mesh of their body and likeness. At the most basic level, this data will unlock the ability to pseudo-anonymously identify and track nearby individuals whenever they are within sight of the XR user.

Identity is just one aspect of a bystander's privacy that will be trivially violated by pervasive, public use of XR. The visual and auditory data captured by an XR device will further enable sensing and processing activities largely in line with what was previously discussed for individual XR users. The key difference is that where an XR user may have reasonably consented to such data capture, bystander data may be captured, processed, retained, and longitudinally refined, all without the bystander's knowledge or consent, and all within the time it takes for a surreptitious glance.

Recommendation made by IEEE Metaverse Governance standard attempt deal with this issue (IEEE 2022). It postulates that, where some aspect of bystander data is legally permissible to be captured and processed, bystanders should be made aware that this capture is occurring and should have the capacity to revoke implicit or assumed consent for capture. Platforms should refrain from enabling the persistent pseudo-anonymous identification or tracking of bystanders and their associated data. Where there is a risk that requested sensor streams enable such tracking and violation of bystander privacy, such streams should be obfuscated by default (e.g., making bystanders unrecognizable).

Overall, it is clear that the current regulatory regime does not capture the capabilities of the XR technologies in the urban planning and conservation. The complexity of the issues in terms of standardisation and privacy protection are such, that require immediate steps to identify the regulatory gaps and fill them with widely accepted policy initiatives.

11 Economic Setting

Assessments of economic potential often use VR and AR technologies equivalently when determining the short- and long-term implications on industry or the work force. Overall, the development potential of VR/AR (or XR) is regarded as high regarding growth and technology innovations in hardware as well as software applications. These technologies are regarded as important in creating new markets but also in changing ones that already exist. One can also find differentiations between VR and AR regarding economic impact, with arguments that at the moment value is mainly created with hardware but that this will shift more towards the creation of content in the future making AR more important in the long run (Kind et al., 2019, p. 30).

Overall, the VR/AR industry is projected to grow quickly in the years to come. As the Fig. 11.1 below shows, this industry has developed and expanded over the last years on the European and global level and is expected to further boom worldwide. By 2030 it is projected to add ca. 1.3 trillion euros to the global economy (PwC 2019, Seeing is believing EC paper 11). Big tech players such as Meta, Google or Microsoft have heavily invested in the VR/AR market and even linked their future progress to the creation of the metaverse. On the European level, the size of the VR/AR market was estimated at 9.6 billion euros in 2021

(growing 26% from the year before). Optimistic estimations of direct employment in this area in Europe range from 440.000 to 860.000 people (Ecorys, 2021, p. 19).

Fig. 11.1. European XR market value (Ecorys, 2021, p. 19)

Across Europe the XR ecosystem has been advancing with regional hubs such as London, Paris, Berlin, Amsterdam or Zurich increasing their activities and establishing their leading positions regarding companies and start-ups. A 2020 survey by Ecorys among industry representatives shows the different characteristics of European companies, such as funding sources, size of companies or the types of products or services provided. Fig. 11.2. below shows that the structure of XR companies is largely smaller to medium sized mainly self- or publicly funded, main products and services are software and content.

Fig. 11.2. Structure of European XR companies (Ecorys, 2021, p. 29).

The main foundation of the development of VR/AR are innovations behind developments of high-tech hardware, which then allow for applications with potentially far-reaching changes to various areas of business. Regarding the potential of innovation specific areas can be identified:

- VR/AR product or service innovation: creation of more efficient products
- VR/AR business model innovation: establishment of unprecedented value propositions or value-capturing methods
- Innovation through businesses/consumer using tech: new services, improving processes, conducting tasks more rapidly (European Commission et al., 2022, p. 37ff).

Comparing the European and the global XR market shows that Europe accounts for about one-third of the global market (see Fig. 11.3 below). This estimation is based on profits of companies providing XR services in the European market (even if these companies may have their headquarters outside of the EU)(European Commission, 2023, p. 100). Yet, as described in more detail below, the positioning of Europe remains challenging regarding awareness and demand for applications and investments compared to the US and Asian market. This can hinder the scaling up of companies if they choose to remain in Europe.

Fig. 11.3. Global XR market- Rest of world vs. Europe 2021 (European Commission, 2023, p. 100)

Next to the high expectations regarding economic growth and employment, specific European challenges can be identified that require attention. Overall, VR/AR technologies are consistently improving, yet the market in Europe is not developing as fast. There is a fragmentation of the VR/AR ecosystem surrounding hardware, software and content creation, meaning that there currently isn't a situation that the entire value chain is connected and ensuring equal access to the digital market. The impact of not addressing this challenge is regarded as very high and also has effects on the potential for scaling up operations by companies. Still, the fragmentation within the European single market due to different regulations or entrepreneurial traditions prove challenging (European Commission, 2023, p. 32ff).

In turn, this situation requires more intensified collaborations such as a creation of a European platform, to connect hardware and software development along European values (e.g., data privacy or ownership) and function as a marketplace for networking (as is the case in the US). More initiatives to build deeper collaborations across the various hubs and country borders continuously can for instance include linking venture capitalists and businesses or supporting start-ups and smaller actors within the XR ecosystem (Ecorys, 2021, p. 86).

To better meet these challenges, the establishment of standards promoting ethical development and ensuring privacy as well as compatibility and accessibility to a global market is regarded as an important step to improve the business environment and foster efficient technology development. Further, standards should help reinforce interoperability and be open to all types of companies (including SMEs).

Regarding the mentioned potential of employment numbers in the area of VR/AR or XR, another challenge is the brain drain of talent in this area. It remains difficult to attract talent to the European sector since many people prefer the US or Asian market with large tech companies offering better salaries and working opportunities as well as an overall richer ecosystem. Access to skills and talent is a key component to fill the needs of European companies and in turn lack of this could obstruct further development in the area of production and content development, in which Europe is currently stronger. Next to competition from other areas of the world, competition between sectors is also relevant. People with appropriate qualifications often prefer other areas with better conditions, such as the video games industry (European Commission et al., 2022, p. 33ff). As technologies VR/AR have the potential to promote diversity (e.g., through diversity in its workforce or environmental sustainability as well as ethical aspects). This is regarded as an area left open by non-European actors especially regarding personal data and privacy. It seems there is the potential for these aspects to be unique characteristics for VR/AR development in the European context even if there is still a need to find ways to measure and quantify these impacts.

Further, raising awareness on VR/AR technologies and applications among consumers and businesses is seen as essential to prevent misunderstanding of the technology. For instance, exhibitions, demonstrations, targeted actions as well as more emphasis on education and training could help spread knowledge on innovative applications and their potential advantages among the general public but also potential talent. Issues of data privacy or ethical and inclusiveness aspects could be addressed early on (Ecorys, 2021, p. 84f). Of course, the funding, financing and investment in the XR industry are key for the economic potential. More targeted funding is suggested to increase the speed of development and adoption, specifically large-scale infrastructure needs (e.g., 5G networks) and projects with the potential for high digital transformation (Ecorys, 2021, p. 87).

Taking the economic development predictions as well as the challenges into account, Europe shows certain strengths such as high innovation potential as well as accordance to certain ethical considerations such as privacy. Also, regulatory frameworks such as the GDPR provide orientation and a leading position in setting global standards for this industry. Difficulties in private funding as well as a lack of big players in the European landscape can inhibit the industry's growth and hinder the development of a skilled workforce. Still, it is regarded that there is a unique (policy) setting in Europe that focuses on a green economy and sustainability, which in turn can deploy the development of XR technologies (Ecorys, 2021). In order to shape the XR innovation landscape research and development also with regard to standardization is needed. For this, interdisciplinary and application-oriented research funding as well as the involvement of SMEs and start-ups is key (Kind et al., 2019).

12 Social and Regulatory Challenges

As we have seen in the sections above, XR technologies are developing in a rapid manner, and they have already created enough expectations to ensure an increasingly strong investment potential. The current penetration of XR technologies in socioeconomic realities is still limited, but the combination of AI and XR capabilities will certainly bring about an exponential growth. And it is exactly this potential that should be in the focus of policymaking, in order to minimise the risks and maximise the benefits of such technological developments.

The risks involved in the development of XR technologies are multifaceted and depend on both the application area and the specific jurisdiction. We have described the relevant risks and challenges that range from generic risks that are seen in almost every digitalised form of technological development, to specific risks revolving around the unique hardware and software employed in XR in specific application areas.

12.1 Social Implications of XR Technologies

Before attempting to identify the specific risk assessment approach that should be followed in the case of XR technologies, it is worth having a short look at what social implications are there as a result of developments in this field. These relate to generalised risks that must be taken into consideration when developing relevant policy initiatives. Whether regulatory initiatives are necessary to deal with these issues, or the existing regulations are sufficient, or even closer and continuous monitoring of the application of law is desirable, is a matter of political decision making. But the identification of relevant risks is the first necessary step to be taken.

12.1.1 Child Safety

Child safety is already a large concern in relation to the internet and social media, with issues such as bullying; harassment or stalking; grooming; doxing; and other forms of violence, threats, and abuse being prominent risks exposed to children. Due to the immersive nature of VR compared to traditional

forms of gaming and social media, the mental impacts of such acts towards children may have a larger impact than if the same incidents occurred in traditional 2D gaming/online environments. Europol (2022) have stated how dangerous metaverse platforms can be for children, outlining 'no (effective) age rating of experiences spaces' offered in the metaverse, online sexual grooming, the potential to physically sexually abuse children using haptics and tactile technology, child pornography production, and the exploitation of children for financial gain through their creation of metaverse content (child labour) as main sources of concern.

Gambling in children has also been observed in these metaverse platforms. Within the Roblox online metaverse environment, children can create games, make profits from the development of games, and purchase collectible items/non-fungible tokens (NFTs). This is made possible through the conversion of real-life currency into the Roblox-platform currency: 'Robux'. These microtransactions made by children, who lack the cognitive ability to understand conversion rates of real-life currency into Robux, have totalled in the thousands without consent from their parents for these expenditures (Tims, 2021). As many collectible items on Roblox are only sold for a limited time, their values skyrocket as soon as they are no longer available to purchase officially from the site. A stock market now exists within the Roblox economy, with children essentially gambling with real life currency to purchase NFTs in the hopes of making a profit, and to simply show off to their peers within the community. However, similar to real life stock market risks, these gambles do not always pay off. Enabling such behaviour within an online environment marketed towards children exposes children to gambling addiction and financial scams (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022).

12.1.2 Psychological Impacts

Immersion in virtual reality worlds can blur the lines between the virtual and the real worlds. VR induces the experiences of 'presence' in another reality, and 'body ownership' in a virtual avatar. 'Presence' constitution is debated, but Slater (2009) described it in terms of 'place illusion' (PI, sense of being in real place), and 'plausibility illusion' (PSI, illusion that scenario being depicted is actually occurring). Slater (2009) states that when 'PI and PSI occur in user at the same time, they will respond realistically to the virtual reality they are in'. However, sense of reality can also disengage XR users. The 'uncanny valley' phenomenon, originally studied in relation to robots, can also be found in avatars in XR environments (Wedel et al., 2020). The 'uncanny valley' is a phenomenon experienced by an individual when a 'representation of a person is highly realistic, but a handful of non-human aspects stand out', causing the individual to feel unsettled and/or repulsed (Immersive Learning News, 2020). The combination of immersion issues and the uncanny valley can result in jarring experiences for users and may further depersonalisation, as previously discussed in the media and entertainment application section.

From a mental health perspective, users can get very emotionally invested in their virtual environments and the virtual characters they interact with, potentially leading to addiction with the long-term impacts of VR addiction currently undetermined (Snijders et al., 2020). Dissociation from reality if one spends time in VR world for too long, which also deepens emotional investment of the individual in their virtual world. Harassment on online platforms and social media is nothing new. However, when harassment occurs within the medium of VR where the user's physiological response is heightened and can be similar to that in real life, this can make the experience of harassment far more realistic and thus may leave the victim with similar psychological trauma as if the incident had happened in the real world (Europol, 2022).

12.1.3 Effects on Relationship

Beyond the data and privacy concerns, critics, such as Turkle (2011), are concerned that using VR for social interactions as opposed to having them in the real world has the potential to negatively impact in-depth conversations and intimacy. With the emergence of adult content on XR technology, this concern applies. With the potential for individuals to no longer want to develop deep and intimate relationships with other humans, and instead resort to receiving physical gratification from a technological source with

minimal to no human interaction. Some researchers are concerned about the negative effects that VR pornography may have on the sexualisation of society and unhealthy sex culture (Wood et al., 2017).

12.1.4 Effects on Democratic Processes

The use of personal data for profiling purposes has led to famous abuses, such as the infamous Cambridge Analytica scandal. Social bots have been used to manipulate political opinions with direct effects in voting behaviours. With the advent of deepfakes, we have reached a deeper level of manipulation that it hard to uncover, even for well-informed users (van Boheemen et al., 2021). XR technologies provide the means for an exponential growth in manipulative potential. On one hand, the amount and quality of personal data that can be collected is unprecedented while on the other hand, the AI capabilities for the creation of manipulative communication increases exponentially. As with the latest applications of GPT4, creating very realistic deepfakes is accessible to everyone, everywhere in the world. The repercussions of such developments in the functioning of our democratic system can be significant and must be dealt with urgently and effectively.

12.2 Regulatory Risk Assessment Approach

Policy making is based on a risk-benefit analysis paradigm that should be adapted to the qualities and particularities of each technology under inspection. As we have no standard assessment processes for new and emerging technologies, we ought to develop a suggestion that can cover the needs of policy making and provide a straightforward, but not simplistic, information source for policy makers. Technology Assessment has established such policy advisory tools that are based on interdisciplinary assessment processes that aim at bringing both scientific and social perspectives in the forefront.

Our suggestion for a risk assessment of XR technologies, on which the future regulatory gap analysis will be based on, derives from existing Technology Assessment approaches to relevant technologies such as virtual reality, augmented reality, artificial intelligence and deepfakes technologies (Horvath et al., 2023; Kaminski et al., 2023; Snijders et al., 2022). These analyses have looked at standard social, economic, and environmental risks of technological developments from the perspectives of science, society and policy alike. XR4Human has already drawn from the current risk assessment literature to identify the main categories of risks relevant to XR as: (i) physical and mental risks; (ii) social risks; (iii) abuse of power; and (iv) legal risks. In addition, a perspective on the peripheral but significant issues of diversity, inclusivity and accessibility, and interoperability, will also be included.

a) Physical and mental risks are the cornerstone of any standard risk assessment of new technologies whether relating to medicines, food, machinery, etc. In the case of XR technologies we have a perfect combination of influence on both the physical and the mental reality with a single instrument. Wearables affecting movements and restricting the physical environment, have at the same time the ability to alter individual consciousness and reality perceptions. This is indeed a unique case of a technological development that impacts the most intimate aspects of human nature. As such policy requires particular attention to this category of risk assessment.

b) Social risks analysis belongs to the standard Technology Assessment approach that receives increasing traction with policy makers. Although these are risks that cannot be easily quantified, they are nowadays acknowledged as an integral part of risk assessment in the application of new technologies. XR technologies have an enormous intrusion potential in the individual's lifestyle and as such, have direct repercussions to societal functions. As we have shown, one obvious risk aspect is that of personal data. XR technologies can easily process biometric data but also secondary physical and mental health data. As these are special categories data, according to the GDPR, the whole XR development can be considered a high-risk category. The combination of XR and AI capabilities can intensify these risks exponentially. Another social risk is the manipulative potential of XR technologies. As

research on deepfakes has shown, nefarious uses of these technologies represent a very present and worrying development that has direct repercussions to our political system. Finally, the usage of XR technologies by very young people, provides another risk perspective in terms of development and education. Child development is specific physical and mental process that is easily affected by environmental stimuli. XR technologies will doubtless influence the development of children whether used for entertainment or educational purposes.

c) Abuse of power risks are relevant to social risks but deserve a special category in terms of regulatory analysis. These risks refer to the current market conditions that have resulted in monopolistic trends and the concentration of control in few dominant players. Data distribution in the global market of digital services, is extremely unequal. A small number of global conglomerates control the vast majority of digital data with grave consequences for society and economy. On one hand, economies suffer from unfair competition whereby dominant players own the resources needed for general technology development and thus diminish the innovative potential of national economies. On the other hand, data can be used for identification of individuals, widespread surveillance and cyber-violence. Private firms or individuals should not have the power to abuse data resources for such purposes.

d) Legal risks focus on a specific aspect of policy making, that of regulatory status. A number of legal instruments already exist to protect citizens from risks deriving from technological developments, albeit these refer to specific developments. When it comes to more generalised technologies such as VR or AU, there are no exclusive legal instruments dealing with them. The result could be either under or over regulation of the field, whereby there is either a vacuum of legal guidance, or a number of overlapping and conflicting guidelines. The risks in either case are significant for developers and users alike and should be explored and brought into the surface of policy debates.

e) The risks in terms of **diversity, inclusivity and interoperability**, should also be part of the regulatory analysis. Interoperability refers to internationally accepted standards that are necessary for a successful and risk-free technological development. At the same time the issues of diversity, inclusivity and accessibility must be explored within the aim of achieving a socially fair and acceptable XR development. Although not strictly regulatory issues, they represent horizontal risks that affect societal interactions with repercussions in the economy and the environment.

13 Towards a Regulatory Analysis

Following the description of the risks that should guide any regulatory analysis in the field of XR technologies, the next step is to identify the existing regulatory landscape that covers the whole field. The following policy initiatives and regulatory frameworks are deemed the most relevant for our purposes:

a) The Artificial Intelligence Act: This is the main European regulation, attempting to cover all fields of AI applications, except military applications. It focuses on the providers of artificial intelligence systems and takes an overall risk approach, whereby the level of perceived risk of the specific application is pivotal for its treatment by the AI Act. Low level risk applications could require only voluntary codes of conducts while high level risk applications will be outright banned in the European Union.

b) The General Data Protection Regulation: This is the main regulation in the European Union dealing with rights of individuals and obligations of service providers in relation to personal data protection and privacy. It attempts to increase control of citizens of the European Union over their data and introduces heavy fines to organisations that undertake illicit exploitation of personal data. The general data protection regulation also applies to personal data that are

transferred between countries from/to the EU and it applies to all individuals and entities that reside in the EU, regardless of origin or citizenship. The regulation has been widely imitated in many countries around the world.

c) Copyright regime: This refers to the copyright law of the European Union but also to related Directives with direct relevance to XR technologies, such as the Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market. Copyright is also affected by international treaties, particularly TRIPS, and as such it represents a regulatory regime with global impact. The issue of the overlap between copyright and patent in XR technology development must also be taken into consideration.

d) Digital Services Act: This is the current regulation updating the Electronic Commerce Directive that attempted to harmonise rules on transparency and information requirements for online service providers within the European Union. While the E-Commerce Directive deals with contracts, liabilities, and codes of conduct in the field (of particular importance is Article 3 that establishes the rules for access to the whole single market) the Digital Services Act attempts to increase the protection of the individual and minimise illegal and exploitative online content. Its risk-based approach and obligations for online service providers to disclose information, is of interest for XR technology developers and users.

e) Audio-visual Media Services Directive: This attempts to regulate the media content by providing obligations to service providers in terms of avoidance of manipulation, accessibility, and protection of minors. It is currently under discussion for updating for an improved harmonisation amongst the EU member states.

Furthermore, there are EU-wide initiatives that have a direct bearing on XR technologies such as the Action Plan on Disinformation or the European Democracy Action Plan. These represent significant policy debates that might lead to future regulatory initiatives that will affect the development of XR technologies.

Each of the above represents a significant aspect of XR technologies and their impact on society, economy, and the environment. There are certainly overlaps that might construe an over-regulation but there are also gaps that signify under-regulation. The mapping of the regulations will follow a hierarchical analysis whereby the regulation will be interpreted in terms of its main scope which in turn will be analysed in terms of jurisdiction coverage, issuing body or organisation, and regulation type. The results of the analysis will identify either a regulatory gap or over-regulation, and their implications in society, economy, or the environment.

The analysis of the current regulatory regime in the European Union will be performed under the categories of Scope of Regulation, Jurisdiction Coverage, Issuing Body or Organisation and Regulation Type. These represent a basic analytical classification for regulatory initiatives to compare their outreach spectrum and enforcement potential.

Fig. 13.1. Regulatory Analysis Categories

At the same time, regulatory gap analysis represents the means to identify aspects of the current regulatory landscape that need amendments due to shortcomings. Policy options will be developed to improve regulations at European level, and these will focus on mitigating the risks and negative impacts that XR technologies could have on society, economy and the environment. Following previous successful examples of developing policy options for the European Parliament (van Boheemen et al 2021) we will structure them according to the following dimensions of policy measures that fit the main impact perspectives of XR technologies:

- a) **Technology:** This refers to the regulations affecting the hardware or software development used in XR applications. It focuses on actors that are involved in the production of XR components.
- b) **Creation:** This refers to policy options that are focusing on the users of the technologies (e.g., application platforms) with the aim of ensuring responsibility in usage of applications and the data that derive from their use.
- c) **Circulation:** This refers to policies covering the dissemination of XR products and the responsibilities that disseminators (e.g., media outlets) have towards consumers.
- d) **Target:** This refers to the regulations focusing on impacts on individual users that are either directly affected by XR applications or non-users that are indirectly affected by them (e.g., bystanders). Physical and/or mental impact aspects are included in this analysis.
- e) **Audience:** This refers to policy options that focus on wider societal impacts that deal with economic, environmental but also democratic functions.

The regulatory gap analysis is the focus of further work in WP3 and, apart from the extensive desktop research, it will also include direct input from relevant stakeholders. This will form part of the forum discussions that are organised within WP1. Feedback from stakeholders will enrich the analysis and improve the acceptance of the subsequent policy recommendations deriving from it.

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